

IMPROVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR PREPARING STUDENTS FOR EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION AND ASSESSING ITS RESULTS

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Abstract. *In this article based on the analysis of scientific research conducted in the world to prepare students of higher educational institutions for technologies and techniques of effective communication, the author determines the current issues of developing specific targeted modular technologies, determining the universal and national moral and aesthetic aspects of verbal and non-verbal means of communication, developing the culture of interpersonal, intercultural and public communication in future specialists, the ability to systematically analyze, think logically and skillfully discuss. In this context, the improvement of pedagogical mechanisms for preparing students of higher educational institutions for technologies and techniques of effective communication is of great scientific and practical importance. The article contains the results of a specific study.*

Keywords: *effective communication, technology and technique of effective communication, verbal and non-verbal means of communication, communicative competence, pedagogical capabilities, moral and aesthetic aspects of verbal and non-verbal means of communication.*

INTRODUCTION

In Uzbekistan, since the first years of independence, it was reached the conclusion about the necessity of training of high qualified specialists in higher educational institutions at level of world standards as an important link of continuous education system, training highly spiritual and welleducated personalities firmly mastered the modern technologies and scientific achievements that have social and communicative activity.

Global movements in the sphere of training of the high qualified specialists in the world in compliance with the requirements of developed democratic state building and civil society assume the training of students of higher education institutions to technologies and techniques of effective communication, development of such professional and personal qualities as communication culture, empathy and speech art. In researches conducted in the world in the sphere of training of higher education students to technologies of effective communication, the significant importance gains the issues of development of certain task-oriented module technologies, definition of human and national moral and aesthetic aspects of verbal and non-verbal tools of communication, development in future specialists the such qualities as culture of interpersonal, intercultural and public communication, moderator and supervision abilities, as well as the ability to analyze comprehensively, to think in a cohesive way and to discuss soundly. In this context, the important research and practical value is the improvement of pedagogical mechanisms of higher education students training to effective communication.

As a result of researches made in the world in the sphere of training the students to technologies and techniques of effective communication, it was obtained the number of scientific outcomes, including: it was developed the multimedia technology — Communication Studies (University of California); it was defined the person-oriented system and role, cognitive,

behavioral constituents of effective communication, as well it was developed the concept of communicative situation and its parameters (Cambridge University); it was developed the complex of social and psychological trainings on development of communicative competence of students (Manchester University); it was improved the mechanisms of effective organization and implementation of interaction with the help of communicative strategies (Kudan Institute of Japanese Language and Culture); it was developed the innovative models of improvement the communication efficiency and interaction (Moscow State University); it was improved the technologies of neurolinguistic programming directed to assurance with efficiency of professional activity of future teacher and development of its communicative competence (Moscow State Pedagogical University); it was developed the technology of students training to effective communication based on the human and cultural approach (Tashkent State Pedagogical University).

A lot of researches in the important areas are being carried out, including the training of future specialists to technology and techniques of effective communication: improvement of communicative technologies based on the subject-subject relationships; development of didactic support to training process to effective communication aimed at ensuring the reasonability of national and advanced foreign experience; development of preventive technologies of elimination the manipulative behavior that occurs in the process of communication.

LITERATURE REVIEW (Analysis and results)

Currently, in the United States, Russia, Britain, Germany, Japan, Uzbekistan and in many other countries, much attention is paid to training of highly qualified specialists by introducing into the educational system the competence-based approach, the theoretical foundations of which were studied by I. Zimney, D. Raven, W. Hutmacher, J. Anderson [1,2,3,4].

In researches by Bystrova Ye., Mykhalskaya A., Ladyzhenskaya T., Mizutani O. and Mizutani N. the specific place is occupied by the problem of communication and rhetorical competence of future teachers; it was developed the theoretical and methodological foundations of effective and complete speech training of future specialists whose professional activity is related to communicative activity [5,6,7,8].

For the last years, the scientists of the world have carried out the researches of communication phenomenon in different spheres of science: philosophical aspects of communication were analyzed the researches of Bueva L., Kagan M., Krauss R., Fefelova V. [9,10,11,12]. The researches on psychology of emotional intellect and effective communication of scientists of CIS countries and far abroad are of the greatest interest in D.Goleman, Karpov A., M.Argyle, Verderber R., and Verderber K., Il'in E., Murav'yova O. [13,14,15,16,17,18]. In the researches by G.Baker, J.Emden, L.Becker, E.Dotcenko and other developed psychological technologies of ways and etchiques of effective communication, as well as the development of communicative competence [19, 20]. The technologies of effective non-verbal communication were studied by J.Burgoon, Butavskaya M., Labunskaya V., Peez A. and Garner A., Birkenbil V. and others [21,22,23,24,25].

Analysis of research works made in recent years in the world shows that the problem of effective communication, interpersonal and communicative competence is one of the most current problems of the interdisciplinary status. It is being actively discussed in the field of philosophy, sociology, cultural studies, linguistics, psychology and pedagogy. The research works of scientists

from different fields of science reveal the essence and content of effective communication, communicative competence.

As this analysis shows, in the 1950s, the term "communicative competence" appears in the Western psychology, and in the 80s, in Russia it was carried out the considerable amount of applied researches in the field of communication and interpersonal relations¹, which reveal the essence of communicative competence as the —system of internal resources required to build effective communicative action (Zhukov Yu.), — such as the level of training of interaction with others, which requires for an individual to operate successfully within their own abilities and social status in the society "(Emelyanov Yu.).

By now, in psychology a lot of concepts, models, approaches identifying the psychological factors that determine the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of communication and interaction were developed. In the summarized form they are as follows: 1) theoretical approaches; 2) empirical models linking the effective communication with the concept of communicative competence; 3) researches where the problem of communication effectiveness is determined by the hierarchical models of interaction; 4) practical social psychology, in which the methods and techniques of effective communication and psychological technologies of communicative competence development are developed.

As a result of the research it was established that as a criteria of communication effectiveness in these concepts are: in behaviorism - the subjective positive assessment of held interaction, in personal approaches - the ability to save the mental health (psychoanalysis) or the possibility of development, personal growth (humanistic psychology), in theories of relevance - the level of cognitive dissonance or congruence, in R.Harre's concepts —achievement of respect, the level of achieved respect. And as the internal personal resources allowing to be effective in communication are: personal determinants, i.e. the lack of personal strain; cognitive characteristics of individual (self-centeredness, decentration, cognitive style), the ability to proper interpretation of the interaction situation, knowledge of samples (scenarios) of social behavior, correct choice of the social mask (R. Harre); role and case normativity, that is, the ability to play a social role, knowledge of engagement rules and compliance of the social behavior of the individual with partner's expectations; communicative skills.

In modern psychological and pedagogical researches, it is emphasized that the communicative competence belonging to the group of key ones, —is an important and integral part of the professional, social and interpersonal competence; it acts as a leading factor of effective communication and largely determines the success and competitiveness of the individual.

The scientific and pedagogical content of key terms as — effective communication — communicative competence were proven in the process of research; their constituent parts were defined as well. According to the analysis results, it is possible to give the definition as follows: — *effective communication* - is the result of interaction of subjects aimed at achieving the mutual understanding between them, at personal development and growth of partners involved in communication, adequate use of methods and techniques of effective communication of relevant certain situation. The leading factors of effective communication are communicative competence, technological approach to communication, knowledge of its theoretical foundations - the content, types, forms, tools, styles, models, technology and techniques, pedagogical possibilities of organizational and technological nature.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In research effective communication is interpreted as the active exchange of information, activity, knowledge, skills and abilities between participants of communication in the positive emotional situation, as the result of the process of achievement of targeted aims through the interaction and self-development.

Technology to communicate effectively - is an effective teaching process allowing expedient to organize the communication, structural and logical approach to communication, successful and productive use of combined forms, methods, techniques and means of communication, finally, it is the well thought-out in every detail the model of communication [28].

Technique of effective communication - is an expression of communicating verbal (word, phrase, language and speech technology; sound, diction, tempo) and nonverbal elements ("body language" - facial expressions, eyes, smile, gestures, movements, posture, etc.) , the ability to read them together and separately. Along with this, it is the management of their emotional state, perception and observation of the companion, the ability to express themselves emotionally and imaginatively, the ability to apply intelligence and creativity in communication.

The followings serve as specific guidelines in the research: preparing students to effective communication, its technology and techniques as the means of personal and professional and personal development; the dynamic nature of the process of preparation of students to technologies and techniques of effective communication; the principle of integrity; the principle of reflexivity and development of emotional intelligence.

The criteria of preparation of students to technology and technique of effective communication consist of the following indicators: motivational, cognitive, activity (readiness), technological and reflexive (Table 1).

Table 1.

The main criteria for students training to technology and techniques of effective communication

Criteria	Content of criteria
Personal and professional-personal reason for this training	Socio-personal reason, understanding of professional and personal importance and necessity of knowledge of the communication basics, its technology and techniques (desire, interest, need)
Knowledge of communication basics and its tools, technologies and techniques, their effectiveness	Knowledge of communication basics, its means - verbal and nonverbal ones, technology and communication techniques, their efficiency and productivity conditions
Willingness and ability to communication technologies, usage of verbal and non-verbal means, their technology.	Planning - designing, forecasting, development of content, organization, manageability, variation by means, by methods and techniques of verbal and non-verbal communication, creation of necessary conditions for effective communication
Verbal and non-verbal communication, technologies and their effectiveness	Achieving the targeted result, efficient communication by means of

	communication technology, speech means, and —body language
Improving the pedagogical communication, its technology and techniques	Deep knowledge of theory and practice of pedagogical communication - pedagogical tact, ethics, communication aesthetics; educational and creative approach to technology and techniques of communication (with students)
Self-assessment of the effectiveness of technological and constructive approach to dialogue, the use of verbal and non-verbal means of communication	Self-analysis and self-assessment achieved in communication (based on the knowledge of theory and practice of communication, its technology and equipment), at social level, among the satisfaction with such communicative experience
Self-improvement of communication culture	Self-improvement of theory and practice of communication, including, the pedagogical one, its techniques and technology and culture as a whole.

The major objective of the research was to develop the model of training students of higher educational institutions to technologies and techniques of effective communication (Picture 1), which is based on axiological and acmeological, competence, active, technological, subject-subject and subject-object, person-oriented and systematic approaches.

Competence-based approach aims to appeal to the range of issues and teacher's authority under extracurricular activities that allow students to carry out their communication addressed to the duties and tasks. Competence is considered by us as the level of preparedness of the individual students, future teachers, to a specific communication activity, to use at the same time knowledge of the communication basics, teaching in particular (with priority human evaluable relation to individual student (pupil). Future teachers' communicative competence is recognized as the willingness of the subject-subject relations based on the person-oriented educational technologies with students.

The activity approach plays an important role in development of communicative competence. As a result of such approach, the students get closer to the role and value of extracurricular activities on the art of communication in personal life and formation, achieving the social status and professional success, and they learn a certain system of knowledge about the theoretical foundations, technologies, techniques of communication, in general, the culture of communication and its communication skills; Students learn at the aesthetic, moral and aesthetic level the verbal and non-verbal means, technology in the process of implementation of various communicative tasks, creative activities.

Technological approach ensures the formation and development of communicative skills associated with the development and implementation of technology of interaction, control and exposure. This ability to follow the prescribed models, to observe the technological discipline, knowledge of various forms of communication, its technology and techniques, verbal and nonverbal means of effective communication, ability to organize modern psychological training,

ability to self-assessment and self-improvement in the field of communication. Subject-subject approach allows you to organize the process of students preparation to technology and techniques of effective communication as a truly human, equitable, creative interaction of teachers and students aimed at their personal and professional development, at mutual enrichment and understanding.

Person-oriented approach creates the conditions for full development of the student's personality, because: 1. It initially determines the student as an active subject of pedagogical interaction stimulating his creative initiative; 2. It promotes the development of personal and social qualities, cognitive interests of students; 3. Relies on subjective experience of students, actualizing the previously acquired knowledge and skills on the theory and practice of human and pedagogical communication, its technology and techniques; 4. It takes into account the individual and psychological- characteristics of each student as much as possible; 5. It allows the student to determine the path of their individual development.

Result and reflective component model consists of diagnostic complex in the form of criteria and level of students readiness to effective communication. Thus, the presented model of students preparation to technology and techniques of effective communication aimed at formation of methodological and logical approaches, principles, pedagogical conditions, methods, forms, factors and resources in the field of training of future teachers to effective communication; development and implementation of technology of students preparation to effective communication, including the stages, content, principles, methods, forms and means of students preparation to effective communication based on the program of communication art.

The essence of the developed technology for students' preparation to effective communication is disclosed by the following scheme: motivation – knowledge- reflection - skills and abilities -workshop – social and communicative experience – self-assessment and self-improvement.

Organizational and technological component of the developed technology includes the principles, techniques, forms, conditions, factors and means of students preparation to technology and technique of effective communication.

Based on the competence-based and technological approaches used in the experimental work, it was determined the effectiveness of forms of development of communicative competence in future teachers: lectures, discussions, dialogue, seminar, workshop, social and psychological training, seminars, consulting, coaching, conference, individual work , pair work, and work in small groups; as well as the innovative methods and forms: lecture-dialogue; lecture – communicative games; quiz; informative and entertaining information; lecture-movies — Culture of communication with discussion; Lecture of pedagogical communication; Lecture-press-conference on the problems of communication; Lecture-consultation on effective communication; Lecture – Lessons of art of communication, individual creativity; Lecture – publication of intellectual and creative works.

Competence-based approach aims to appeal to the range of issues and teacher's authority under extracurricular activities that allow students to carry out their communication addressed to the duties and tasks. Competence is considered by us as the level of preparedness of the individual students, future teachers, to a specific communication activity, to use at the same time knowledge of the communication basics, teaching in particular (with priority humane valuable relation to individual student (pupil).

Future teachers' communicative competence is recognized as the willingness of the subject-subject relations based on the person-oriented educational technologies with students. Experimental research was conducted in Jizzakh, Navoi and Kokand State Pedagogical Institute and Tashkent State Pedagogical University from 2005 to 2015 and it consisted of a recital, forming and final experimental work. To the diverse experimental work carried out by the pedagogical opportunities of students 76 training to the technologies and techniques of effective communication, it was attracted totally 300 teachers and 600 students. In experimental researches 600 students took part (300 in the control ones and 300 - in experimental ones). The total sample size of the research was 600 people at a grand total population of 900 people. Below are the final results of students training to technology and techniques of effective communication after participation in workshops and social and communicative activities, statistical processing of results of the experimental work (Picture 2) and the chart of readiness level of students to technology and techniques of effective communication.

Picture 1. Students' preparation model to the technology and techniques of effective communication

To confirm the results of the research it has been applied the statistical analysis of results of experimental work. The level of academic performance of students in the experimental and control groups was assessed in three areas (high, medium, low) at all stages of the pilot studies according to specific criteria: motivational, cognitive, creative, active, technological and reflexive evaluation. As can be seen from the table, the overall performance of the experimental group above the critical criterion that allows us to draw a conclusion about the effectiveness of the research proves the accuracy of the experimental results of training. Statistical data processing indicates the reliability of the results obtained in the experimental groups, based on which it can be concluded the effectiveness of the pilot program, conducted research as a whole. To confirm the results of the research it has been applied the static analysis of the results of experimental work. The level of academic performance of students in the experimental and control groups was assessed based on three indicators (high, medium, low) at all stages of the pilot researches according to specific criteria: motivational, cognitive, creative, active, technological and reflexive and evaluation (Picture 2). As can be seen from the table, the overall performance of the experimental group is above the critical criterion that allows us drawing the conclusion about the effectiveness of the research, it proves the accuracy of experimental training results. Statistical processing of data shows the authenticity of results obtained in the experimental groups, based on which the effectiveness of the pilot program and research made in general can be confirmed as well. These data show that the average results obtained in the experimental group are higher for 19% than on the control group. As the research result, the conclusion has been made on the optimal use of pedagogical opportunities of extracurricular conditions in preparation of students to technology and technique of effective communication, pedagogical validity and efficiency of developed theoretical and practical bases of pedagogical high schools' students preparation to technology and techniques of effective communication, communicative activity.

Picture 2. Chart on the level of readiness of students to technology and technique of effective communication

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Studies in recent years, scientific research in our country show the existence of the need for higher education institutions improve the training of future specialists for effective communication and pedagogical mechanisms of their globalization of thinking. Revealed the usefulness of extracurricular training opportunities in the implementation of these issues in the higher education institutions as the development of modular technology, focused on a specific

goal, improving the moderator and Supervising practice, identifying human and national moral and aesthetic aspects of verbal and non-verbal means of communication, the development of communicative and emotional culture of the future specialists.

As for the dissertation topic, the nature communicative culture, communication, its structure, types, styles, means, factors of efficiency, communication and activity, its criteria were considered in the work. It was developed the content of pedagogical high schools' students training to technology and techniques of effective communication on the example of extracurricular classes on author's program "Art of Communication".

Identified and substantiated based on the examples of classes the opportunities of extracurricular work in students preparing to technology and technique of effective communication within the author's educational system. The theoretical and pedagogical, practical bases of the problem have been developed. It was shown the experimental training of pedagogical high schools' students to technology and technique of effective communication at extracurricular classes on mastering the art of communication, in particular, its technology and technique.

As the result of successful experiment, it was tested the developed and scientifically proven theoretical and pedagogical, practical aspects of the problem, it was obtained the positive results, based on which the relevant theoretical and pedagogical, practical positions, conditions, conclusions were established, adjusted and classified into the certain system, and the recommendations were developed as well.

The successful solution of the problem is due to several factors: definition and justification of the research idea, the author's concept, system and pedagogical, practical approach to its implementation. The aims and objectives of the study were positively resolved as a result of provision of conceptual approaches, teaching theoretical and practical basis and the actual process of communication on social and communicative level.

CONCLUSION.

The practical significance of the study is determined by drawing the models of organization of innovative activity of teachers in preparing students for effective communication, interpretation from a pedagogical point of view of the nature and content of the basic concepts for the study, the implementation of extracurricular activities program on the art of communication, aimed at preparing students for effective communication practice in universities.

The theoretical significance of the research: in the actualization of the meaning of the training of students; Disclosure of pedagogical possibilities of solving the problem; optimal conditions in the system; theoretical teaching and practical basis.

Main conditions, conclusions and recommendations were tested, implemented and applied in teaching practice of high schools. Availability of confirmation of their pedagogical efficiency and sufficient high effectiveness in preparing students to technology and technique of effective communication, in improving the communicative professional and pedagogical knowledge and capabilities.

Special attention in the preparation of students for the technology and equipment to communicate effectively paid to strengthening cooperation "teacher - student", "teacher - student", "student - student." Important importance in the integration of higher education institutions to pedagogical, psychological subjects with extracurricular classes.

Preparation of students of higher educational institutions to effective communication is seen as a personal, social and public and professional-pedagogical problem of national importance,

as is aimed at education of socially active young generation in social and communicative sphere, with independent thinking, able to express freely and accurately their thoughts.

REFERENCES

1. Zimnyaya I.A. Klyuchevye kompetentsii – novaya paradigma rezultata obrazovaniya//Vysshee obrazovanie segodnya. 2003.–№ 5.–P.12-13.
2. Raven Dzh. Kompetentnost v sovremennom obshchestve: vyyavlenie, razvitie i realizatsiya. /Dzh.Raven M.: Kogitotsentr, 2002. –396 p.
3. Hutmacher Walo. Key competencies for Europe//Report of the Symposium Berne, Switzerland 27-30 March, 1996. Council for Cultural Cooperation (CDCC) //Secondary Education for Europe Strasburg, 1997.
4. Anderson J. (1988). Communication competency in the small group. In R. Cathcart & L. Samovar (Eds.), Small group communication, A reader. Dubuque, IA: Wm. Brown.
5. Bystrova E.A. Tseli obucheniia russkomu iazyku, ili kakuiu kompetentsiiu my formiruem na urokakh russkogo iazyka//Obuchenie russkomu iazyku v shkole: Ucheb. posobie dlia dlia studentov pedagogicheskikh vuzov. -M.: Drofa, 2004.
6. [Mikhalskaia A.K. Pedagogicheskaiia ritorika: istoriia i teoriia: Ucheb. posobie dlia stud. ped. universitetov i institutov. M.: Izdatelskii tsentr «Akademiia», 1998. – 432 p.
7. Ladyzhenskaia N.V. Obuchenie uspeshnomu obshcheniiu: Rechevye zhanry / N.V. Ladyzhenskaia. Pod red. T.A. Ladyzhenskoi. – M., 2005.
8. O.Mizutani, N. Mizutani, How to Be Polite in Japanese.—Tokyo, 1987.—160 p.
9. Bueva L.P. Chelovek: deyatelnost i obshchenie. M.: Mysl, 1978. – 216 p.
10. .Kagan M.S. Mir obshcheniya: Problema mezhsobektnykh otnoshenii. - M.: Akademiya, 2008. – 319 p.
11. Krauss R.N. Poznanie i obshchenie. /V kn. «Poznanie i obshchenie». – Moskva: Nauka, 1988. – P. 81-94.
12. Rodermel T. A. Fenomen kompetentnosti v sovremennom obrazovanii: sotsiokulturnyi aspekt. ... diss.kand. filosof.nauk. –Tomsk, 2011. – 168p.
13. Fefelova V.I. Ponyatiya «obshchenie», «kommunikatsiya», «kommunikativnaya kultura» v filosofskom aspekte // Prikladnaya psikhologiya i psikhoanaliz. – 2007. №1. – P.27-31.
14. Goleman D. Emotional intelligence: Why it Can Matter More Than IQ?/D.Goleman.-N.Y. Bantam Books,1995.
15. Argyle M., Furnham A., Graham J.A. Social situations. –L.: Cambrige University press, 1981. – 256 p.
16. Verderber R., Verderber K. Psikhologiya obshcheniia. — SPb.: PRAIM_EVROZNAK, 2003. — 320 p. (Seriiia «Glavnyi uchebnyk»).
17. Ilin E.P. Psikhologiya obshcheniia i mezhlchnostnykh otnoshenii. – SPb: Piter, 2009. – 576 p.
18. Muraveva O. Psikhologiya kommunikativnoi kompetentnosti: teoreticheskie i prakticheskie aspekty / O.Muraveva – LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing GmbH&Co.KG, 2011 – 136 p.

19. Greg S. Baker. *Fitly Spoken: Developing Effective Communication and Social Skills*. – Brighton Publishing LLC, 2011. – 212 p.
20. Joan van Emden, Lucinda Becker. *Effective Communication for Arts and Humanities Students*. Palgrave Macmillan. June, 2003.–224 p.
21. Dotsenko E.L. *Psikhologiya manipulyatsii: fenomeny, mekhanizmy i zashchita* – M., 1997. – 344 p.
22. Burgoon, J. K. (1994). Nonverbal signals. In M. L. Knapp & G. R. Miller (Eds.), *Handbook of interpersonal communication* (2nd ed., p. 229–285). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
23. M.L. Butovskaia "Iazyk tela: priroda i kultura" -M.:Nauchnyi mir, 2004.– 440 p.
24. Labunskaja V.A. *Ne iazyk tela, a iazyk dushi! Psikhologiya neverbalnogo vyrazheniia lichnosti*. – Rostov-na-Donu, 2009. – 344 p.
25. Piz A., Garner A. *Iazyk razgovora*. M.: Izd-vo EKSMO-Press, Izd-vo EKSMO-MARKET, 2000. 224 p.
26. Birkenbil V.F. *Iazyk intonatsii, mimiki, zhestov /Per. s nem.* – SPb: Piterpress, 1997. – 214 p.
27. Riukle Khorst. *Vashe tainoe oruzhie v obshchenii. Mimika, zhest, dvizhenie*. M.: AO «Interespert», 1996. – 280 p.
28. Nurmanov A.T., Mustafakulov A.A. *Managing the Quality of Training of Pedagogical Personnel's on the Basis of TQM - (Total Quality Management)// International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, Vol. 24, Issue 05, 2020. – P.3759-3770.*